

Supplementary Material S1

For

Eusociality and the transition from biparental to alloparental care in termites

Libraries used: (ggplot2, aomisc, drc, MASS). Codes simplified from R script.

Figure 2A

Notes: observing the changes in population size (total number of individuals in colonies at the time of opening), over time. Use of a quadratic function (poly2) where a strong quadratic effect was observed.

```
>ggplot(colonygrowth, aes(age,number))+geom_point()+stat_smooth(method = lm, formula = y ~ poly( x, 2))
```



```
>lm(formula = number ~ poly(age, 2, raw = TRUE), data = colonygrowth)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	4.9343903	6.9492308	0.710	0.479
poly(age, 1, raw = TRUE)	0.1455518	0.1006714	1.446	0.150
poly(age, 2, raw = TRUE)	0.0014223	0.0002525	5.634	8.03e-08 ***

Residual standard error: 36.17 on 156 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.8519, Adjusted R-squared: 0.85

F-statistic: 448.7 on 2 and 156 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Figuer 2B

Note: all castes variables were transformed as a binary output, so that when a given colony was opened, it was positive or negative for a given caste. The presence/absence of a caste was plotted as a function of the day post foundation. Each model was performed separately, but In figure 2B, all models were graphically combined, and the proportion of colonies with a given caste presents was used as the Y axis for the dataplot, instead of the binary plot.

Eggs

```
> ggplot(castes, aes(age, Eg))+geom_point () + stat_smooth(method="glm", method.args=list(family="binomial"), se =TRUE)
```



```
> Egg<-glm(Eg~age, data=castes, family=binomial(link="logit"))
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-5.73128	2.04260	-2.806	0.00502 **
age	0.26417	0.08978	2.942	0.00326 **

Null deviance: 100.126 on 115 degrees of freedom

Residual deviance: 17.734 on 114 degrees of freedom

```
>dose.p (Egg, p=0.5) #for median emergence day for eggs
```

	Dose	SE
p = 0.5:	21.695	2.3026

Larvae

```
> ggplot(castes, aes(age, L1))+geom_point () + stat_smooth(method="glm", method.args=list(family="binomial"), se =TRUE)
```



```
La<-glm(L1~age, data=castes, family=binomial(link="logit"))
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-14.1869	5.7079	-2.485	0.0129 *
age	0.3432	0.1374	2.498	0.0125 *

Null deviance: 136.649 on 115 degrees of freedom

Residual deviance: 13.491 on 114 degrees of freedom

```
> dose.p(La, p= 0.5) #for median emergence day for larvae
```

Dose SE
 p = 0.5: 41.332 2.021

Workers

```
> ggplot(castes, aes(age, Wor))+geom_point () + stat_smooth(method="glm", method.args=list(family="binomial"), se =TRUE)
```



```
> W<-glm(Wor~age, data=castes, family=binomial(link="logit"))
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-11.38863	3.38162	-3.368	0.000758 ***
age	0.18150	0.05233	3.469	0.000523 ***

Null deviance: 154.933 on 115 degrees of freedom
 Residual deviance: 22.678 on 114 degrees of freedom

```
> dose.p(W, p= 0.5) #for median emergence day for workers
```

Dose SE
 p = 0.5: 62.745 2.9992

Soldiers

```
> ggplot(castes, aes(age, Sol))+geom_point () + stat_smooth(method="glm", method.args=list(family="binomial"), se =TRUE)
```



```
> S<-glm(Sol~age, data=castes, family=binomial(link="logit"))
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-10.87926	3.00500	-3.620	0.000294 ***
age	0.15479	0.04169	3.713	0.000205 ***

```
> dose.p(S, p= 0.5) #for median emergence day for soldiers
      Dose    SE
p = 0.5:  70.285  3.1073
```

Figure 2C

Note: binary data of colonies alive/dead at 280 d was used in this analysis, as a function of the day when all workers were removed. Because of the confirmed absence of colony survival when workers removed beyond 150 d post foundation, five values of 0 were added at day 175 obtain the model estimation beyond 161 d. In figure 2C, proportion of colonies alive was used as the Y axis for the dataplot, instead of the binary plot.

```
> ggplot(Survival, aes(age, status))+geom_point () + stat_smooth(method="glm", method.args=list(family="binomial"), se =TRUE)
```



```
> Sur<-glm(status~age, data=Survival, family=binomial(link="logit"))
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	5.27566	0.94780	5.566	2.60e-08 ***
age	-0.04962	0.00875	-5.672	1.42e-08 ***

```
> dose.p (Sur, p=0.5)
      Dose    SE
p = 0.5: 106.313  5.5191
```

Figure 2D. no model used, just a confirmation that the number of worker increased over time, with the Pearson correlation values provided on figure and in text. Made for visualization of live/dead colonies after removal of workers.

Figure 2E

Note: binary data of colonies with more than 15 workers (0 to 15 worker = 0, 16 and above =1) was used in this analysis, as a function of the day after foundation. Because of the confirmed presence of more than 15 workers in all colonies after 120 d, five values of 0 were added at day 175 obtain the model estimation beyond 161 d. In figure 2E, proportion of colonies alive with more than 15 workers was used as the Y axis for the dataplot, instead of the binary plot.

```
> ggplot(W, aes(age, W15))+geom_point () + stat_smooth(method="glm", method.args=list(family="binomial"),se =TRUE)
```



```
>glm(W15~age, data=W, family=binomial(link="logit"))
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	-10.38168	2.35900	-4.401	1.08e-05 ***
age	0.11158	0.02493	4.476	7.62e-06 ***

```
> dose.p(WW, p=0.5) # to determine the median day when colonies have at least 15 workers
```

	Dose	SE
p = 0.5:	93.039	3.5564

Figure 2F

Notes: This is a simple observation of the gain of individuals 50 after all workers were removed. In addition to the Pearson correlation values provided in text and figure, a linear model confirms the progressive loss of the brood in colonies that had their workers removed over time.

```
> ggplot(Ga, aes(age,gain))+geom_point()+stat_smooth(method = lm, formula = y ~ x)
```



```
> lm(formula = gain~age, data =Ga)
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	18.42806	2.05269	8.978	6.63e-15 ***
age	-0.30383	0.02181	-13.932	< 2e-16 ***

Residual standard error: 11.44 on 114 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.63, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6267

F-statistic: 194.1 on 1 and 114 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Figure 3C and 3 D

Notes: In both figures, the analysis of the change of wet weight in queens and kings was first visualized using the ggplot "loess" and "gam" methods to determine the cut off values for each phases. In addition to the linear models provided here, the respective Pearson correlations values were also used in the main text and the figures.

Queens:


```
>lm(Qw~age,data = Qw1) # gaining weight phase for queens
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	7.42365	0.16002	46.39	< 2e-16 ***
age	0.06703	0.00798	8.40	1.3e-10 ***

Residual standard error: 0.7507 on 43 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.6213, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6125

F-statistic: 70.56 on 1 and 43 DF, p-value: 1.296e-10

```
>lm(Qw~age,data = Qw2) # losing weight phase for queens
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	11.867492	0.319826	37.11	< 2e-16 ***
age	-0.047429	0.004199	-11.30	1.88e-14 ***

Residual standard error: 0.509 on 43 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.748, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7421

F-statistic: 127.6 on 1 and 43 DF, p-value: 1.88e-14

```
>lm(formula = Qw ~ age, data = Qw3) # stagnant weight phase for queens
```

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	7.166334	0.207269	34.575	<2e-16 ***
age	-0.001591	0.001108	-1.435	0.154

Residual standard error: 0.5127 on 108 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.01871, Adjusted R-squared: 0.009627

F-statistic: 2.06 on 1 and 108 DF, p-value: **0.1541**

Kings:

>lm(Qw~age,data = Qw1) **# gaining weight phase for kings**

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	7.42365	0.16002	46.39	< 2e-16 ***
age	0.06703	0.00798	8.40	1.3e-10 ***

Residual standard error: 0.7507 on 43 degrees of freedom
 Multiple R-squared: 0.6213, Adjusted R-squared: 0.6125
 F-statistic: 70.56 on 1 and 43 DF, p-value: 1.296e-10

> lm(formula = Kw ~ age, data = Kw2) **# Loosing weight phase for kings**

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	12.310095	0.385937	31.90	< 2e-16 ***
age	-0.060857	0.005066	-12.01	2.5e-15 ***

Residual standard error: 0.6143 on 43 degrees of freedom
 Multiple R-squared: 0.7704, Adjusted R-squared: 0.7651
 F-statistic: 144.3 on 1 and 43 DF, p-value: 2.496e-15

> lm(Kw~age,data = Kw3) **# stagnant weight phase for kings**

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	5.9427102	0.1778121	33.421	<2e-16 ***
age	-0.0005252	0.0009509	-0.552	0.582

Residual standard error: 0.4399 on 108 degrees of freedom
 Multiple R-squared: 0.002817, Adjusted R-squared: -0.006417
 F-statistic: 0.3051 on 1 and 108 DF, **p-value: 0.5819**

Figures 3C and 3D

Notes: In both figures, the analysis of the change of dry weight in queens and kings was first visualized using the ggplot "loess" and "gam" methods to determine the initial dynamic of the weight. After comparing non-linear model (ΔAIC), a logistic model was found to be the best fit for both datasets.

Queens dry weight

```
> Mq<-drm(Qdry ~ age, fct = L.4(), data = Dry)
Model fitted: Logistic (ED50 as parameter) (4 parms)
Parameter estimates:
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
b:(Intercept)	0.0448441	0.0057463	7.8040	3.506e-13 ***
c:(Intercept)	1.2376371	0.0251259	49.2574	< 2.2e-16 ***
d:(Intercept)	3.4689702	0.1896290	18.2935	< 2.2e-16 ***
e:(Intercept)	39.6943325	5.3372739	7.4372	3.138e-12 ***

Residual standard error: 0.2456349 (196 degrees of freedom)

```
> R2nls(Mq)$PseudoR2
PseudoR2 = 0.8863081
```

Plot creation:

```
> Qpred <- as.data.frame(predict(Mq, newdata = data.frame(Qdry = seq(1:255)), interval = "confidence"))
> Qpred$x <- 1:255
> ggplot(Dry, aes(x = age, y = Qdry)) + geom_point() + geom_ribbon(data = Qpred, aes(x = x, y = Prediction, ymin = Lower, ymax = Upper), alpha = 0.2) + geom_line(data = Qpred, aes(x = x, y = Prediction))
```

Kings dry weight

```
> Mk<-drm(Kdry ~ age, fct = L.4(), data = Dry)
Model fitted: Logistic (ED50 as parameter) (4 parms)
Parameter estimates:
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
b:(Intercept)	0.0959472	0.0095051	10.094	< 2.2e-16 ***
c:(Intercept)	0.8997292	0.0189696	47.430	< 2.2e-16 ***
d:(Intercept)	2.6573228	0.0306939	86.575	< 2.2e-16 ***
e:(Intercept)	74.8947764	1.2131765	61.734	< 2.2e-16 ***

Residual standard error: 0.1942221 (196 degrees of freedom)

```
> R2nls(Mk)$PseudoR2
PseudoR2 = 0.9399628
```

Plot creation:

```
> Kpred <- as.data.frame(predict(Mk, newdata = data.frame(Kdry = seq(1:255)), interval = "confidence"))
> Kpred$x <- 1:255
> ggplot(Dry, aes(x = age, y = Kdry)) + geom_point() + geom_ribbon(data = Kpred, aes(x = x, y = Prediction, ymin = Lower, ymax = Upper), alpha = 0.2) + geom_line(data = Kpred, aes(x = x, y = Prediction))
```

Figures 3E and 3F

Notes: In both figures, the analysis of the change of nitrogen amount in queens and kings was first visualized using the ggplot "loess" and "gam" methods to determine the initial dynamic of nitrogen content. Average values were used because of the necessity to pool samples owing to the sensitivity of the Elemental Analyzer. Each dataset was split into two distinct phases: a

significant decrease in nitrogen in the first phase, then an increase in nitrogen in the second phase. After comparing non-linear model (ΔAIC), a Weibull function was found to be the best fit for both datasets for each phase. Each phase was therefore analyzed separately, with an overlap in use of data between the two phases during the nitrogen minimal period to obtain the early/end tails of the minimal plateau.

Queens

(plots produced with the same approach as for Figure 3C and 3D)

Phase 1

```
>modelQN1 <- drm(QNave ~ age, fct = W1.4(), data = N1)
```

Model fitted: Weibull (type 1) (4 parms)

Parameter estimates:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
b:(Intercept)	2.0020778	0.2745856	7.2913	1.808e-06 ***
c:(Intercept)	0.0979993	0.0063522	15.4275	5.010e-11 ***
d:(Intercept)	0.2300406	0.0048747	47.1905	< 2.2e-16 ***
e:(Intercept)	70.5079333	3.9357141	17.9149	5.188e-12 ***

Residual standard error: 0.006713425 (16 degrees of freedom)

```
> AIC(modelNQ1) = -137.8512
```

```
> R2nls(modelNQ1)$PseudoR2
```

PseudoR2= 0.9827945

Phase 2

```
modelQN2 <- drm(QNave ~ age, fct = W1.4(), data = N2)
```

Model fitted: Weibull (type 1) (4 parms)

Parameter estimates:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
b:(Intercept)	-7.9910340	3.7092635	-2.1543	0.04426 *
c:(Intercept)	0.1052953	0.0034913	30.1593	< 2.2e-16 ***
d:(Intercept)	0.1305399	0.0028131	46.4038	< 2.2e-16 ***
e:(Intercept)	139.4152223	6.8626221	20.3152	2.397e-14 ***

Residual standard error: 0.006872986 (19 degrees of freedom)

```
> AIC(modelNQ2) = -158.2103
```

```
> R2nls(modelNQ2)$PseudoR2
```

PseudoR2 = 0.691884

Kings

(plots produced with the same approach as for Figure 3C and 3D)

Phase 1

```
>modelKN1 <- drm(KNave ~ age, fct = W1.4(), data = N1)
```

Model fitted: Weibull (type 1) (4 parms)

Parameter estimates:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
b:(Intercept)	4.5004978	0.4718332	9.5383	5.280e-08 ***
c:(Intercept)	0.0704474	0.0035321	19.9447	9.987e-13 ***
d:(Intercept)	0.2231644	0.0031850	70.0679	< 2.2e-16 ***
e:(Intercept)	81.3871130	1.5136018	53.7705	< 2.2e-16 ***

Residual standard error: 0.007259444 (16 degrees of freedom)

```
> AIC(modelKN1b) = -134.7234
```

```
>R2nls(modelKN1b)$PseudoR2
```

PseudoR2 = 0.9896912

Phase 2

```
> modelKN2 <- drm(KNave ~ age, fct = W1.4(), data = N2)
```

Model fitted: Weibull (type 1) (4 parms)

Parameter estimates:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
b:(Intercept)	-7.7992612	4.0342297	-1.9333	0.06824 .
c:(Intercept)	0.0720311	0.0024776	29.0726	< 2.2e-16 ***
d:(Intercept)	0.0902871	0.0019115	47.2332	< 2.2e-16 ***
e:(Intercept)	138.9059863	6.4445377	21.5541	8.065e-15 ***

Residual standard error: 0.004809147 (19 degrees of freedom)

```
> AIC(modelKN2) = -174.6359
```

```
> R2nls(modelKN2)$PseudoR2
```

PseudoR2 = 0.7010151